

THE BIG BANG MERGERS OF PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS -A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF HOW MERGERS AND ACQUISITIONS OF BANKS IN INDIA SHAPED THE BANKING INDUSTRY

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***Abstract:** All across the world there have been a spate in merger and acquisition in banking space some because of failing banks, some to achieve economy of scales and some to come together to create world level bank. More importantly in India its combination of these three factors as well as the need to have a balance sheet to meet the Basel guidelines and to make a staunch establishment in other economies. Though India have seen more of merger based on synergies , geographical approach and long term implications of merger still common banking software has also been a key consideration for same. The mergers which have recently taken place have to some extent achieved the objective of government. Since the recent mergers have not merged distressed banks to strong banks there is no significant effect on asset quality of the merged entity. The growth rate in retail banking sector have been phenomenal in recent times and there is a view that their mergers will lead to create one of world largest banks .The consolidation in banking industry has been based on value creation , enhanced customer experience , geographical approach and to increase capital base. Liberalization and reforms by successive governments with advancement in technologies have made the industry more competitive. The emergence of private sector banks, foreign bank and the new liberal grant of payment bank license had also pushed the Indian public sector banks to try to outperform their peers. The paper focus on pros and cons of merger of public sector banks.*

Keywords: Mergers, Banks, Public Sector, Acquisitions, Banking

I. INTRODUCTION

As per Von (2010) a large firm tends to survive better in turmoil and challenges of industry rather than a small firm because of its size and capability of managing economies of scales. The mergers and acquisitions in banking domain are now very common with banks expanding their operation over economies through mergers and acquisitions. The firm contends that this is a strategy to gain competitive edge over rivals while on other hand many argue that it thwarts competition and creates monopoly. Kumar (2012) argues that merger of strong and dominant player leads to killing of competition and creating monopoly wherein large firm's controls majority share of market and the smaller firms dies its natural death failing to survive and succumbing to unequal competition. In long term it is contended that dominant player will lose value over a time because of no competitive offerings. Through this paper we will look at the relevance of banking mergers in the Indian Diaspora.

It was in the year 1969 when the government led by Mrs. Indira Gandhi bought 14 banks under nationalization with the aim to make banking reach every citizen of the country. These banks occupied nearly eighty five percent of market shares at that time and after 6 more banks was nationalized in 1980 the percentage went up to ninety one percent. In 1993 merging of new bank of India with Punjab National Bank was the first ever merger of public sector banks taking the number from twenty to nineteen. This was partly due to the liberalization policy of the government which brought globalization to doorsteps of India. This era was followed by many M&A's in nearly every sector hence changing the very basic structure of industry. This was also looked from different point of view as it led to consolidation of power in hands of strong conglomerate and also promoted vast economic power in hands of few. Though Antitrust Law of India looks into every merger still by Act of parliament the mergers of public sector bank has been kept of its ambit whereas regulation and competition should go hand in hand so that the banks stability is not affected by merger. Allahabad Bank was founded in 1865 by Europeans in the city that it gets its name from. It has the distinction of being the second-oldest modern bank in India after the State Bank of India, which started as Presidency Bank in Calcutta in 1806. Indian Bank, on the other hand, started as a purely Swadeshi enterprise after the failure of Arbuthnot bank, a major British bank based in Madras. This prompted Indian nationalist and lawyer V Krishnaswamy Iyer to establish Indian Bank with the support of the Chettiar community. Incidentally, Indian Bank was established on August 15, 1907, exactly 40 years

before

India's

independence.

In today's economy major source of credit comes from Banks who have over period of time enhanced their service delivery, discovered new ways of credit dispensation and performed well despite strong regulatory requirements. Banks have supported many organizations to achieve economy of scales by funding their acquisitions domestically and internationally. In simple terms, a merger occurs when two different firms join their operations to form one single organization (Braggion, Dwarkasing & Moorey, 2010). Economies of scales is realized when large firms benefit from the cost advantages of large scale production (Ashton & Pham, 2007). Large banks are able to diversify their operations and therefore they can effectively provide banking services at a lower price and also deliver sustainable returns to its investors (Braggion, Dwarkasing & Moorey, 2010).

Banks Merged Since 1969 Nationalization (Source : Bloomberg)

Years	Number of Banks Merged
1970s	6
1980s	8
1990s	8
2000s	11
2010 onwards	19
Of which in	
2017	6
2019	10
Total	53

Banks Acquirer (Since 1969)

Source : Ministry of Finance & <https://www.bloombergquint.com/opinion/the-origins-of-the-great-indian-bank-merger>

There are no sources in the current document. State Bank of India	9
Bank of Baroda	5

Punjab National Bank	5
Union Bank of India	4
ICICI Bank	3
Oriental Bank of Commerce*	3
Bank of India	2
Canara Bank	2
HDFC Bank	2
Indian Bank	2
New Bank of India**	2
United Bank of India***	2
Allahabad Bank****	1
Central Bank of India	1
Centurion Bank*****	1
Centurion Bank of Punjab*****	1
Federal Bank	1
IDBI Bank	1
India Bulls	1
Indian Overseas Bank	1
ING Bank	1
LIC	1

*Since Merged with Punjab National Bank (2019)

**Since Merged with Punjab National Bank (1991)

***Since Merged with Punjab National Bank (2019)

****Since Merged with Indian Bank (2019)

*****Since Merged with Bank of Punjab

*****Since Merged with HDFC Bank

BANK MERGERS

S.No.	Name of Bank	Nationalised	Merged With	Year
1	State Bank of India	1955		
2	Bank of Baroda	1969		
3	Bank of India	1969		

4	Central Bank of India	1969		
5	Punjab National Bank	1969		
6	Canara Bank	1969		
7	UCO Bank	1969		
8	Indian Overseas Bank	1969		
9	Union Bank of India	1969		
10	Indian Bank	1969		
11	Bank of Maharashtra	1969		
12	Punjab & Sind Bank	1980		
13	Bhartiya Mahila Bank	Started as PSB	SBI	2017
14	State Bank of Bikaner & Jaipur		SBI	2017
15	State Bank of Patiala		SBI	2017
16	State Bank of Travancore		SBI	2017
17	State Bank of Mysore		SBI	2017
18	IDBI	Started as DFI	Sold to LIC	2018
19	Dena Bank	1969	Bank of Baroda	2019
20	Vijaya Bank	1980	Bank of Baroda	2019
21	Syndicate Bank	1969	Canara Bank	2019
22	Allahabad Bank	1969	Indian Bank	2019
23	United Bank of India	1969	Punjab National Bank	2019
24	Oriental Bank of Commerce	1980	Punjab National Bank	2019
25	Andhra Bank	1980	Union Bank of India	2019
26	Corporation Bank	1980	Union Bank of India	2019

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

For this study researcher have took into account various articles and studies since various mergers have took place. Most notably Anand Manoj & Singh Jagandeep study of impact of merger of banks on the merging entity namely Bank of Punjab with Centurion Bank, Times bank with HDFC Bank , Global Trust Bank with Oriental Bank of Commerce and Bank of Madurai with ICICI Bank and ICICI limited with ICICI Bank. The study revealed that all these mergers increased share holder value in terms of wealth. Unlike US where after merger value of share holder was hit badly, in India it was totally opposite. In 2018 study of merger of SBI with its associate Bank and Bhartiya Mahila Bank by Jai Bansal and Dr.Gurudatt kakkar it was concluded that the merger enhanced the profitability of the bank.

Azeem Ahmed Khan study of 2011 explains the motives of Mergers & Acquisitions in India. It concluded that M&A's helped in increasing earnings per share as well as it provided for declaration of dividend to share holders.

Berger and Humphrey (1997) study of efficiency of banking sector focused on developed markets banking with focus on US market.

As per study of Castillo and McAniff of 2007 are used by firm as a strategy to kill competition and capture majority market share. One of rational is to achieve branch network growth by way of acquisition.

In 2016 paper by Kotnal Jaya Shree the economic impact of merger of associated bank with SBI concluded that gross profit , net profit , profit margin , DER have substantially increased post merger. The dichotomy it reflected was although merger and acquisitions have proved beneficial but it is not a solution to organization in financial distress.

Kuriakose Sony et al in its 2009 study, studies the valuation practices adopted in merger of bank and how share swap was worked out.

Ziharias 1997 did a brief study on banking sector with specific reference to syndicate bank in comparison to other banks and examined various aspects of capital adequacy, asset quality, profitability and efficiency. Not only dividend has been affected positively but also many financial parameters viz Earnings Per Share before Interest and Tax , Current Ratio , Interest Coverage Ratio , Operational Cost efficiency has also been positively affected.

III. ADVANTAGES OF M&A IN BANKING SECTOR

Merger is associated with coming together of synergies to increase profitability and reach economies of scale. Some advantages of mergers are –

1. To create world level banks of similar size and stature ;
2. Greater efficiency with technological advancement;
3. To consolidate Public Sector Banks to reduce unnecessary and unhealthy competition between them ;
4. To keep in line with vision of making India a \$5 Trillion economy.
5. Improve market reach and increased revenue.

IV. INDIAN BANKING SECTOR REFORMS

Narsimhan Committee which was setup by government of India in Dec 1997 submitted a report in 1998 stressing on merger of banks. The committee proposed

- Merger of banks for operational resilience and increasing book size of bank to inch toward making it a global bank ;
- Restructuring and strengthening of legal framework of recovery of bad debts ;
- Three tier of banking in India out of which 2-3 must be bank of international stature , 8-10 national level banks a high network of local banks
- To merge large banks to create a largest bank of global stature and recognition , similarly it stressed on merging's of banks of equal stature viz merging of weak banks with weak banks and strong banks with strong banks ;
- Push for computerization and technological advancement of customer offerings ;
- Review of framework of recruitment , manning of branches , staffing , remuneration procedures and training processes of the Bank
- Review of Bank Nationalization Act , RBI Act , SBI Act as well as Banking Regulation Act
- Set up of banking boards which have professionals and thus decisions taken should be professionally

Though the entire committee report could not have been implemented still over a period of time many recommendations have found a place in banking system.

India is a developing country and since liberalization the ten years which followed is famously known as decade of merger it has becoming the order of the day. Policy of government, attractive investment destination, and economic stability of nation has led to mergers in India.. Earlier works has been done on framework of policies market trends and human capital thus ignoring the greater focus on profitability and efficiency of merger which is the focus of this study.

V. IMPLICATIONS OF MERGER PROS and CONS

PROS:

1. Earlier merger of associate banks and Bhartiya Mahila Bank has resulted in huge benefit to customer which has increased more regional presence of the bank. With merger of more banks in 2017 & 2019 customer outreach have become much more better ;

2. Currently no Indian Bank figures in top 50 list of global banks , with recent mergers it's expected that sooner we will find Indian Banks in the league;
3. Rationalization of branch reach will help reduce costs and reaching economy of scales ;
4. It will decrease unethical competition between public sector banks and give stiff competition to private sector banks ;
5. Technological advancement and combined treasury will lower down the cost to income ratio;
6. Share of merged banks have created wealth for share holders.
7. In case of Indian Bank which is predominantly south Indian bank and Allahabad Bank which is primarily north Indian bank , the merger have bought an entirely new synergy.

CONS:

1. Post merger cultural and HR integration is still an issue ;
2. Due to government direction to provide equal promotion favoritism has affected employees moral ;
3. There is a negative impact on P&L since welfare funds which is still at same limit as prescribed by GOI is unable to cover all employees and retirees welfare.

VI. CONCLUSION

Though the aim of consolidation was to create banks that can be recognized as banks of global structure much is yet to be done to meet that challenge. The mergers were mooted to give strength to weak and failing banks and those under PCA to effectively come out of their illness since failure of any bank in banking system of any developing country is viewed as a threat to financial stability of that economy. Though the earlier consolidation and mergers in Indian Banking Industry happened on behest of RBI to save the failing banks and to compulsorily merge weak banks with strong banks yet the new mergers have been mooted by government for whole set of other reasons such as scaling new heights, achieving new goals , improved profitability and to achieve economies of scale. Mergers and consolidations are no solution for

curing bad assets, redundant technology and operational inefficiency yet it's a requirement of future. The aim should be creation of such strong banking entity which can withstand testing times of failing economy and recession also. A merger should not be exercised as an option to merge old generation public sector banks gobbling with inefficient management, lax attitude, and poor asset quality to burden a good quality bank which is making profit every year. The mergers can only be justified when it generates net profit creating wealth to shareholders majority in which is the state in case of public sector banks. Also to meet new Basel norms, capital adequacy norms which are going to be more stringent in coming years need is to build such large banks therefore Mergers in banks will become inevitable in future. It can be safely assumed that though consolidation will help in maintaining liquidity and capital adequacy but still the merged entity will be exposed to any unexpected system risk. All studies concludes that after merger, the new banks net profit will be reduced and stability will be affected but the merger of Indian bank and Allahabad Bank which is the case study of the research has proven it otherwise. Going forward issues like cultural integration, technological advancement in asset protection, regional balancing of presence should be taken care of for proving and making banking merger a huge stupendous success and which is a step in direction of becoming a global bank.

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